

PACIFICUS

A LITERARY MAGAZINE

Print: 3082-4060
Online: 3082-4079

VOLUME 1

ISSUE 2 | APRIL - JUNE ISSUE
A QUARTERLY PUBLICATION

- Poetry
- Short Stories
- Essays
- Spotlight on Emerging Writers
- Creative Corner
- Others

PACIFICUS

A Literary Magazine (Print & e-Publication)

Volume I, Issue II | A Quarterly Publication

ISSN (Online): 3082-4079 | ISSN (Print): 3082-4060

Publisher: Binas Publishing

Email: binasbookers2013@gmail.com

JILL ROSE P. ADOR, MSCrim

Instructor 2

Negros Oriental State University

jillrosepajulasador@gmail.com

"A MOTHER'S LAMENT AND HOPE"

O Lord, my God, I called him mine,
Fruit of my womb, a gift divine.
I nursed him near, I sang him grace,
I taught him truth in early days.

He rose one dawn with eyes of flame,
Desire for more, for wealth, for name.
He left my arms, the fold, the light—
And vanished deep into the night.

I wept upon the threshing floor,
And laid his sandals by the door.
Each night I watch the distant hill,
My soul waits quiet; my hands are still.

"Spare him, O Lord," my spirit cries,
"Though he has gone where mercy dies.
Though he has spent his soul in dust,
Still You are faithful, still You are just."

His tunic torn, his pride laid bare,
I dream he turns with matted hair.
With heart of ash and eyes of rain,
He seeks the path back home again.

For had I thousand lambs to give,
I'd trade them all that he might live.
But greater still, Thy mercy runs—
To call the lost, to claim the sons.

And should I see him yet once more,
Worn and weary at my door,
I'll clothe him not in wrath or shame,
But bless him in the Father's Name.

O God of Jacob, hear my plea—
Let grace pursue him back to me.
And if he comes, or if he roam,
Still I shall watch. Still I'll call home.

